

Design, synthesis and spectral characterization of chelates of Pd^{II}, Pt^{II} and Rh^{III} with 6-guanidino-2,4-dimethyl-3,5-diazine and 6-phenyl guanidino-2,4-dimethyl-3,5-diazine-potential ligands with biological interest

Durgadas Mukherjee* and Soumendranath Das

Department of Chemistry, Mahadevananda Mahavidyalaya, Monirampur, Barrackpore,
Kolkata-700 120, India

E-mail : durgadas.mukherjee@gmail.com

Manuscript received 18 July 2007, revised 7 November 2007, accepted 19 November 2007

Abstract : Complexes of 6-guanidino-2,4-dimethyl-3,5-diazine and 6-phenyl guanidino-2,4-dimethyl-3,5-diazine with Pd^{II}, Pt^{II} and Rh^{III} have been reported. Complexes have been characterised on the basis of analytical, magnetic and spectral characterization and powder diffraction studies. Crystal field parameters have also been calculated. The Pd^{II} and Pt^{II} complexes are square planar as expected and Rh^{III} complexes are pseudo-octahedral. IR data indicate that the imino nitrogen of the guanidine residue and one of the pyrimidyl nitrogen atoms acts as bonding sites in the formation of these complexes.

Keywords : Palladium, platinum, rhodium, guanidino pyrimidines.

Introduction

Synthesis and characterization of metal complexes with pyrimidine, pyrazole, pyrimidino-pyrazole and pyrazolopyridyl ligands with Pd^{II}, Pt^{II} and Rh^{III} have been reported earlier¹. The present communication deals with the report of isolation and spectral characterization of a number of Pd^{II}, Pt^{II} and Rh^{III} complexes of two strategically designed bidentate ligands, 6-guanidino-2,4-dimethyl-3,5-diazine (GPym, Fig. 1a) and 6-phenyl guanidino-2,4-dimethyl-3,5-diazine (PGPym, Fig. 1b). The complexes may have biological potency². The ligands contain guanidine and pyrimidine moieties. Both moieties are well known for having biopotency together with coordinating ability to metal ions.

Results and discussion

Table 1 presents analytical data of complexes. Conductance measurement in DMF indicates that Pd^{II} and Pt^{II} complexes are non-electrolytes and Rh^{III} complexes behave as (1 : 1) electrolyte, the species being truly represented as [Rh(PGPym/GPym)₂X₂]X [X = Cl, SCN]. Over all solubility of the complexes in common solvents is very poor. All the reported complexes are diamagnetic.

Electronic spectra :

Upon Gaussian analyses of the reflectance spectra of

the examined Pd^{II} and Pt^{II} complexes, four bands are obtained at ~18250, ~20350, ~25550 and ~32250

Fig. 1

Table 1. Analytical data and pertinent properties of Pd^{II}, Pt^{II} and Rh^{III} complexes

Complexes	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)				Conductivity	$\nu(\text{M-N})^a$	$\nu(\text{M-N})^b$
	M	C	H	N			
[Pd(GPym)Cl ₂]	30.96 (31.93)	24.28 (24.51)	3.16 (3.20)	19.86 (20.42)	11	235	520
[Pd(GPym)(SCN) ₂]	27.48 (27.52)	21.45 (21.66)	2.65 (2.83)	25.05 (25.27)	9	240	525
[Pt(GPym)Cl ₂]	43.46 (43.96)	19.54 (19.94)	2.58 (2.61)	15.98 (16.61)	13	245	535
[Pt(GPym)(SCN) ₂]	39.26 (39.72)	18.22 (18.01)	2.46 (2.35)	17.86 (18.01)	22	240	530
[Rh(GPym) ₂ (Cl) ₂ Cl]	-	30.98 (31.14)	4.15 (4.07)	25.82 (25.95)	38	230	540
[Rh(GPym) ₂ (SCN) ₂ SCN]	-	27.52 (27.68)	3.70 (3.62)	30.14* (29.98)	42	250	545
[Pd(PGPym)Cl ₂]	25.08 (25.48)	36.95 (37.25)	3.46 (3.58)	16.78 (16.71)	12	230	535
[Pd(PGPym)(SCN) ₂]	23.12 (23.01)	33.28 (33.62)	3.17 (3.23)	20.92* (21.13)	6	235	530
[Pt(PGPym)Cl ₂]	36.82 (37.24)	30.98 (31.37)	3.15 (3.01)	14.18 (14.07)	8	245	540
[Pt(PGPym)(SCN) ₂]	33.96 (34.13)	28.64 (28.77)	2.82 (2.76)	18.18* (18.07)	12	255	525
[Rh(PGPym) ₂ Cl ₂ Cl]	-	45.24 (45.11)	4.42 (4.33)	20.32 (20.24)	38	260	530
[Rh(PGPym) ₂ (SCN) ₂ SCN]	-	40.94 (41.10)	3.86 (3.95)	24.14* (23.97)	40	250	540

*Including nitrogen present in thiocyanate. ^aPyrimidine, ^bGPym/PGPym.

cm⁻¹ respectively. Such transitions in order of increasing energy suggest square planar environment around metal ions³. The first low-energy spin allowed band in the region ~18250 cm⁻¹ has been assigned to the transition $b_{2g}(d_{xy}) \rightarrow b_{1g}(d_{x^2-y^2})$. In MCl_4^{2-} [M = Pd^{II}, Pt^{II}] this transition was observed between ~16700–17600 cm⁻¹. The blue shift may be taken into account in the light of stereochemical difference between the ligand and the chloride ion. The bands at ~25500 and ~32260 cm⁻¹ are spin allowed transitions. Using known relationships⁴ Δ_1 , Δ_2 and Δ_3 were calculated to be Δ_1 (~25000 cm⁻¹), Δ_2 (~9560 cm⁻¹) and Δ_3 (~3850 cm⁻¹) respectively. Therefore Δ_1 is greater than ($\Delta_2 + \Delta_3$). These observations strongly suggest square planar geometry of the complexes. In all complexes the value of Δ_1 is much larger than that of Δ_2 . It is because σ donor ligands cause marked destabilization of the $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbital while d_{xy} level remains practically non bonding. The electronic absorption spectra of DMF solutions of Pd^{II} and Pt^{II} complexes exhibit strong absorption peaks below 23000 cm⁻¹ which probably envelop the expected bands in a square planar envi-

ronment. A number of spectral bands between 31000–43000 cm⁻¹ with very high molar extinction coefficient [$\epsilon_{\text{max}} \approx 10^4$] are observed. These are ascribed to M-L π CT bands coupled with inter/intra ligand transitions⁵ and the bands occurring at ~32250 cm⁻¹ are attributable π - π^* (C \equiv N) transition of ligands.

The diamagnetic spin-paired octahedral Rh^{III} has $^1A_{1g}$ ground state configuration. Two absorption bands observed at ~21750–22450 cm⁻¹ and ~29550–30320 cm⁻¹ are attributable to two spin-allowed transitions $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1T_{1g}(\alpha_1)$ and $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1T_{2g}(\alpha_2)$ respectively. Additional two bands in the regions of 15000–15850 cm⁻¹ and 19250–19750 cm⁻¹ may be taken as split components of $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1T_{1g}$ transition into $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1E_g$ and $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1A_{2g}$, in order of increasing energy. The splitting of lower energy absorption bands to a very much greater extent is an indication of examined species as trans-isomer. The values of different crystal field parameters $\alpha_2/\alpha_1 \sim 1.36$ –1.39, $10 Dq$ (22680–24590 cm⁻¹), B (495–550 cm⁻¹) and ligand field stabilization energy (12–12.5 kcal/mol) were calculated, from known relationships⁶ and are in good

R = H/C₆H₅M^{II} = Pd/Pt

X = Cl/SCN

M^{II} = Rh

X = Cl/SCN

agreement with an octahedral Rh^{III} ion. Decreased values of B as compared to a corresponding free ion value of 720 cm^{-1} suggest a considerable overlap with a strong covalency in the metal-ligand bond. Reduced values of B are also associated in the reduction of effective cationic charge.

The effective cationic charge values ($\sim 1.52\text{--}1.58$) are considerably below the formal (+3) oxidation state of Rh^{III}. In DMF, the complexes, in addition to $d\text{--}d$ bonds, exhibit bands around 33850 cm^{-1} which on may be as-

signed to $\pi\text{--}\pi^*$ ($\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$) transitions of the ligands.

¹H PMR spectra : The characteristic ¹H NMR spectral data of Pd^{II} and Pt^{II} complexes of PGPym and GPym as compared to those of the uncomplexed ligands (Table 2) reveal that there is downfield shift of protons, except protons of the guanidine moiety present in the ligands and protons present in the phenyl group of PGPym. Protons bonded to the nitrogen of guanidine moiety of the molecules do not appear in the spectra and they might have undergone exchange with HOD present in the solvent. The significant change in the chemical shift of C-4 proton of PGPym and GPym occurs as this proton is closest to the bonding sites of the ligands. This change provides an additional support for participation of pyrimidyl nitrogen atom of the ligand.

IR spectra : Bands in the 3μ region arising due to γ_{asy} (N-H) [$3350\text{--}3390\text{ cm}^{-1}$] and γ_{sy} (N-H) [$3320\text{--}3140\text{ cm}^{-1}$] modes of vibration of the guanyl group are observed almost in the same positions as those in the original ligand molecules with slight decrease in intensities suggesting participation of ligands in complex formation without deportation. The $\gamma(\text{C}=\text{N})$ stretching bonds of the guanidine part of both the ligands appearing around 1650 cm^{-1} has been found to experience a (-ve) shift of $(10 \pm 5)\text{ cm}^{-1}$ pointing to the probable involvement of the imino nitrogen of the guanidine moiety of the ligands in complex formation with metal ions. IR bands due to diazine (pyrimidine) system appearing around 1540 cm^{-1} [$\gamma_{\text{C}=\text{C}}$] in the free ligand have been found to experience shifts in the higher energy side ($\Delta\gamma \sim 15 \pm 5\text{ cm}^{-1}$) in the metal complexes indicating, thereby, the expected participation of the pyrimidyl ring nitrogen in the complexation. Far-IR spectra further suggest that appearance of new bonds in the range $230\text{--}260\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $520\text{--}545\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which may be safely assigned to $\gamma_{\text{M-N}}$ (Pym)⁸ and $\gamma_{\text{M-N}}$ (guanidine)⁹ [M = Pd^{II}, Pt^{II} and Rh^{III}].

The far-IR spectra of the present Pd^{II} and Pt^{II} complexes show the presence of two strong to medium-strong $\gamma_{\text{Pd-Cl}}$ (at 315 and 290 cm^{-1}) and $\gamma_{\text{Pt-Cl}}$ (at 340 and 325 cm^{-1}) confining *cis*-geometry. For Rh^{III}, trans-struct-

Table 2. ¹H NMR data of Pd^{II} and Pt^{II} complexes in DMSO-*d*₆

	<i>a</i>	<i>b</i>	<i>c</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>e</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>g</i>
Free ligand	6.66	2.22	2.22	ab	ab	ab	7.2
Pd(PGPym)Cl ₂	6.78	2.30	2.36	ab	ab	ab	Unchanged
Pt(PGPym)Cl ₂	6.66	2.32	2.36	ab	ab	ab	Unchanged
Pd(GPym)Cl ₂	6.78	2.30	2.34	ab	ab	ab	-
Pt(GPym)Cl ₂	6.66	2.32	2.36	ab	ab	ab	-

ab = absent.

ture is suggested on the appearance of one $\gamma_{\text{Rh-Cl}}$ (medium-strong) band at 280 cm^{-1} . In Pd^{II} and Pt^{II} thiocyanate complexes, strong sharp bands at $2055\text{--}2080\text{ cm}^{-1}$ are observed due to $\gamma(\text{C}\equiv\text{N})$ stretching of the coordinated thiocyanate group. The $\gamma_{\text{C-S}}$ stretching band is located at $685\text{--}720\text{ cm}^{-1}$, indicating a sulphur-bonded SCN. Only one band is obtained in the region 2175 cm^{-1} instead of two split bands in case of *cis*-attachment of the thiocyanate group¹⁰. *Trans* configuration is suggested due to the appearance of one $\gamma(\text{Rh-SCN})$ [medium-strong band at 280 cm^{-1}] and sulphur bonded thiocyanate is indicated by appearance of $\gamma_{\text{C-S}}$ stretching bond at $685\text{--}720\text{ cm}^{-1}$.

Powder X-ray diffraction : The photographs of Pd^{II} and Pt^{II} complexes under investigations contain a large number of lines, many of which are weak. This suggests that the complexes crystallize in low symmetry. X-Ray powder patterns showed no traces of unreacted ligand in the metal complexes¹¹.

Experimental

All the materials used in the preparation of Pd^{II} , Pt^{II} and Rh^{III} complexes were analR quality and were used without further purification. Spectro grade DMF was used for spectral and conductance measurements. DMSO-*d*₆ (Aldrich) was used for recording ¹H NMR data. The ligands GPym and PGPym were prepared by condensation reactions of free biguanide bases with acetylacetone by the modification of earlier method¹². Free biguanide and free phenyl biguanide bases were isolated from normal biguanide sulphate and phenyl biguanide hydrochloride. The ligands GPym (m.p. $242 \pm 2\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) and PGPym (m.p. $200 \pm 2\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) were characterized by elemental analyses, IR, NMR and mass spectra.

Synthesis of metal complexes :

Chloro complexes : The acidic aqueous solution of each M(II) chloride [M(II) = Pd^{II} / Pt^{II}] (pH ~ 3.4) (2.5 mmol in 20 ml water) was mixed with an ethanolic solution of the ligands (2.5 mol) and the resultant yellowish brown solution was refluxed for half hour on a steam bath and then left for 3 to 4 h at room temperature. The precipitated compounds were filtered off, washed with ice-cold water-ethanol (1 : 1) mixture and finally dried over fused CaCl_2 . Chloro complexes of Rh^{III} were prepared in the same way by taking Rh^{III} chloride and ligands in 1 : 2 ratio. The complexes were dirty yellow in colour.

Thiocyanato complexes : The thiocyanato complexes were prepared by metathesis reactions from chloro complexes.

Analytical results and conductance values are presented in Table 1. Pd and Pt were estimated by standard procedures. Magnetic susceptibilities of the complexes were measured by Gouy balance using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{SCN})_4]$ as the calibrant. The diffuse reflectance of the complexes was taken with Carry-17D spectrophotometer with a reflectance attachment Model No. 1711. The electronic spectra of the metal complexes were recorded in DMF using same spectrophotometer. IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer (Model No. 77) using CsI phase. X-Ray powder diffraction photographs of the ligands and a few representative complexes of Pd^{II} and Pt^{II} were taken with a Debye-Scherrer Camera of diameter 114.6 nm using a copper target [$\text{CuK}\alpha = 1.542\text{ \AA}$], operating voltage was 33 kV with tube current of 10 mA, time of exposure was 8 h. The 80 MHz PMR spectra of the ligands and one Pd^{II} complex [$\text{Pd}(\text{PGPym})\text{Cl}_2$] and one Pt^{II} complex [$\text{Pt}(\text{GPym})\text{Cl}_2$] in DMSO-*d*₆ were recorded on a Varian CFT-20 NMR spectrometer.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (DM) is thankful to UGC for financial assistance (MRP). The authors are grateful to Mr. Subhas Maikup, R.S.I.C., Eastern Zone, Dr. D. K. Ghosh of the Institute of Central Glass and Ceramic Research Institute, Kolkata, Dr. D. Sengupta, Principal cum Secretary of Mahadevananda Mahavidyalaya and Prof. Dulal Chandra Mukherjee for their help during the work. Finally this presentation is dedicated to Late Dr. Nityananda Saha who made one of the authors (DM) able to work in the field of Coordination Chemistry.

References

1. N. Saha and D. Mukherjee, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1988, **125**, 213; N. Saha, D. Mukherjee and D. Bhattacharya, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1987, **137**, 161; N. Saha, D. Bhattacharya and S. K. Kar, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1982, **67**, L37; N. Saha, A. Saha and A. Misra, *Polyhedron*, 1994, **13**, 2025.
2. M. J. Clare, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1974, **12**, 349.
3. S. I. Shupack, E. Billing, R. J. H. Clark, R. Williams and H. B. Gray, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, **86**, 4594.
4. (a) W. R. Mason III and H. B. Gray, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **90**, 5721; (b) C. J. Balhausen and H. B. Gray in "Coordination Chemistry", ed. A. E. Martell, New York, p. 64.
5. A. B. P. Lever, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1968, p. 354; H. B. Gray and C. J. Ballhausen, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **85**, 260.
6. P. C. Jain, H. L. Nigam and A. Mehara, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1970, **32**, 2933.
7. S. P. Ghosh, P. Bhattacharjee, L. Dubey and L. K. Mishra, *J*

- Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, **54**, 234; N. Nakanishi and P. R. Solomon, "Infrared Absorption Spectroscopy", 2nd ed., Holden-Day, San Francisco, 1977, p. 257.
8. I. A. Dorrity and K. G. Orrel, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1974, **36**, 230.
9. I. R. Doring and D. W. Wertz, *Appl. Spectros.*, 1968, **22**, 63; I. R. Doring, L. Layton, D. Link and B. Mitchel, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1965, **21**, 1367; A. D. Alien and T. Theophanides, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1964, **42**, 1551.
10. J. Chatt and L. A. Duncanson, *Nature (London)*, 1956, **178**, 997.
11. M. Goodgame and K. W. Jones, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1980, **46**, 23.
12. S. N. Poddar and A. Sarkar, Private communication.